

A study on the colour reaction of molybdenum(V) with 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-theinyl)-4H-chromen-4-one and its applications

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Molybdenum(V), obtained from molybdenum(VI) by reduction in presence of ascorbic acid, has been determined spectrophotometrically. Mo^V formed an intense yellow colour with 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-theinyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (CHTC) in sulphuric acid medium which showed an absorption maximum at 424 nm. This method was found to be rapid, more sensitive than other methods and free from several common interferences including vanadium and tungsten.

Various chromone derivatives¹⁻⁶ have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI} in different acid media. But, the sensitivity, selectivity and Beer's law range was low. Mo^V obtained by reducing Mo^{VI} with ascorbic acid has given an intense yellow colour with 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-theinyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (CHTC) in sulphuric acid medium, which formed the basis of the proposed method of molybdenum determination after extracting the Mo^V-CHTC complex into chloroform. The sensitivity of the method was found to be higher than other chromones reported¹⁻⁶ to form binary complexes with molybdenum and the system was free from several common interferences, including vanadium and tungsten. The procedure was rapid and had been applied to various natural and industrial samples with satisfactory accuracy.

Results and discussion

Molybdenum(VI) formed a light yellow colour with CHTC in neutral medium and an intense yellow colour in acidic medium. However, Mo^V obtained by ascorbic acid reduction⁷ in 1 M H₂SO₄, formed a more intensely coloured complex with this reagent having absorption maximum at 424 nm. Reduction by hydrazine sulphate has given low absorbances in both H₂SO₄ and HCl medium of 1 M acidity and hence was not advantageous. The order of decreasing absorbance of Mo^V-CHTC complex in chloroform was found to be H₂SO₄ > HCl > CH₃COOH > H₃PO₄ when extracted at 1 M acidity in each case, in the presence of ascorbic acid. The influence of H₂SO₄ concentration on the reduction and extraction behaviour was studied in terms of absorbance and it was observed that a constant and maximum absorbance was obtained when Mo^V was reduced by adding ascorbic acid to an aqueous phase containing be-

tween 0.5–2 M H₂SO₄ and extraction of the complex was made at 0.1–1.5 M H₂SO₄. The acidities outside the optimal range of reduction and extraction has decreased the absorbance. Hence both the reduction and extraction steps were carried out at 1 M H₂SO₄ for further investigations. The effect of variables on the absorbance of Mo^V-CHTC complex was studied by keeping the concentration of molybdenum 1.0423 × 10⁻⁵ M. A constant absorbance for 0.2–3 ml of 5% solution of ascorbic acid was observed by varying its concentration in a total 10 ml aqueous phase. It has been observed that absorbance decreased significantly at higher amounts of ascorbic acid. Therefore, 1 ml of 5% ascorbic acid was used in further studies.

The absorbance was increased initially by increasing the CHTC concentration, which attained constancy for 0.8–1.8 ml of 0.1% ethanolic solution, but decreased at higher concentration with the formation of turbidity in the reagent blank.

During shaking of the aqueous phase with the solvent the absorbance of the complex increased, reaching a plateau in 10–30 s, and then falls gradually on further increasing the equilibration time.

Under optimum conditions, the extraction behaviour of the Mo^V-CHTC complex was studied. The quantitative (100%) extraction of the complex was done into chloroform, dichloromethane, carbon disulphide and carbon tetrachloride, but maximum absorbance was obtained in chloroform. The partial extraction of the complex was found into toluene, 1,2-dichloroethane, benzene, isopentyl alcohol, butyl acetate, isopentyl acetate, isobutylmethyl ketone, ethyl acetate and diethyl ether and negligibly into cyclohexane and 1-butanol. A single extraction with an equal volume of chloroform has given quantitative extraction of the complex. The stability of the complex was studied for 24 h in chloro-

form and the absorbance remained unchanged.

On the basis of the above investigation, the optimum conditions giving maximum absorbance were incorporated into the given procedure.

The absorption spectrum of the Mo^V-CHTC complex against the reagent blank showed λ_{max} at 424 nm.

The spectrum of reagent blank against pure solvent (chloroform) has shown that the reagent absorbs strongly upto 410 nm and thereafter the absorbance decreases significantly at 424 nm.

Beer's law, standard deviation and sensitivity : Beer's law was found to obey over a range of 0–2.6 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$ of solvent phase, however, the practical range of determination of molybdenum as obtained from the Ringbom curve⁸ was 0.21–1.95 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$ of solvent phase at 424 nm. The standard deviation was 0.0012 absorbance units for ten replicate determination of 1.0 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$ in aqueous phase. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method at 424 nm were 5.32 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0018 $\mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Stoichiometry of the complex : On the basis of Job's method of continuous variations⁹, as modified by Vosburg and Cooper¹⁰ for the two phase system, the curves obtained by taking equimolar solutions of molybdenum and CHTC at two different concentrations (1.04×10^{-4} and $2.08 \times 10^{-4} M$), waiting for 1 min after mixing and measuring the absorbance at two different wavelengths 424 and 440 nm, indicated that the extracted species has a composition, Mo : CHTC = 1 : 2. This was further confirmed by the mole-ratio method¹¹, where the concentration of one component was fixed at $2.08 \times 10^{-5} M$ for the first set and $4.17 \times 10^{-5} M$ for the second and that of the other component was varied. The absorbance was measured at 424 and 440 nm as above.

Effect of diverse ions : Under optimum conditions the effects of various anions, complexing agents and cations on the absorbance of Mo^V-CHTC complex were studied by taking 1 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$. Nitrate (40); sulphate (35); chloride (30); thiourea (25); acetate (20); carbonate, iodate, metabisulphite, iodide, persulphate and borate (5 each); phosphate (3); tartrate, citrate and EDTA (0.6 each); fluoride (0.5) and oxalate (0.3) caused <1% error. All the anions and complexing agents were added in the mg ml^{-1} amounts given in parentheses as their solid sodium salts except iodide, metabisulphite, iodate, persulphate and bromide, which were added as potassium salts. Glycerol ($\leq 4\%$ v/v) and potassium thiocyanate ($\leq 0.002 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$) gave 1% error.

The absorbance of the Mo^V-CHTC complex was not affected by the presence of various cations such as Mg^{II}, Ca^{II},

Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, Cr^{III}, As^V, Al^{III}, Bi^{III} and V^{IV,V} up to 1 mg ml^{-1} each; Ag^I up to 0.6 mg ml^{-1} ; Pb^{II}, U^{VI} and Th^{IV} up to 0.5 mg ml^{-1} each; Zr^{IV}, Ni^{II} and Se^{IV} up to 0.1 mg ml^{-1} each; Ti^{IV}, Nb^V and Ta^V up to 0.05 mg ml^{-1} each; Rh^{III}, Os^{VIII}, Pd^{II}, Re^{VII}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III}, Au^{III} and Ir^{III}, up to 0.01 mg ml^{-1} each (higher amounts were not tested); Sn^{II} up to 0.003 mg ml^{-1} and W^{VI} up to 0.002 mg ml^{-1} , when added in 10 ml of aqueous phase had caused <1% error. Sb^V even in traces gave >1% error. Fe^{III} and Cr^{VI} upto 1 mg ml^{-1} caused <1% error in the presence of 0.3 ml of 5% ascorbic acid solution added per ml of aqueous phase.

Application : The proposed method has much better sensitivity than the methods reported earlier^{1-6,12-17} which have made use of chromones, Sn^{II}-thiocyanate, dithiol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, hydroxylamine-PAR and mercaptoacetic acid. When compared with these^{3,5,14} the present method had a wide Beer's law range, better precision and accuracy and freedom from interferences from several important elements. The method is simple and takes only 10 min for a single determination and much less in series operation. The satisfactory accuracy and precision limit have shown the usefulness and applicability of the method to a wide variety of synthetic and technical samples, especially flue dust and steels. The results (average of triplicate analyses) obtained were : reverberatory flue dust (Mo added 40 μg , found 40.2 μg); BCS 406/1 (Mo content 1%, found 0.972%), BCS 219/4 (Mo content 0.58%, found 0.56%) and BCS 261/1 (Mo content 0.11%, found 0.11%).

Experimental

A UV-visible spectrophotometer (Systronic 118) with matched 10 mm cells was used for absorbance measurements. Stock solution of Mo 10 mg ml^{-1} was prepared by dissolving sodium molybdate dihydrate (E. Merck) in deionised water was standardized by the oxine method¹⁸. Solutions at lower concentration levels were prepared by appropriate dilutions.

Ascorbic acid (S.R.L., A.R.) was dissolved in deionised water to give 5% (w/v) solution. 6-Chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-theinyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (CHTC) was prepared by literature method¹⁹ and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.1% (w/v) solution.

Chloroform (Qualigens, SQ) was distilled and the fraction distilling at 60–61° was used for extraction. Other chemical used were of A.R. quality. Steel and reverberatory flue dust samples were dissolved as reported earlier⁶.

Procedure : An aliquot (1 ml) containing $\leq 26 \mu\text{g Mo}$ was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel to which added 2

ml of 5 M H₂SO₄, 1 ml of 5% of ascorbic acid, 1 ml of 0.1% ethanolic solution of CHTC and 5 ml of H₂O and mixed well. The solution was then equilibrated with equal volume (10 ml) of chloroform for 25 s. After separation, the solvent phase was passed through a Whatman (No. 41) filter paper to remove water droplets. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 424 nm against reagent blank. The molybdenum content was read off a standard curve prepared under similar conditions.

Modification for W, Nb, Ta and Sn : When ≤ 0.02 mg of W^{VI}, ≤ 0.5 mg each of Nb^V and Ta^V or ≤ 0.03 mg of Sn^{II} were present, 6 mg of sodium citrate, 5 mg of sodium fluoride or 6 mg of disodium EDTA were added, respectively, to the aqueous phase before the addition of CHTC. Otherwise, the entire procedure remains the same.

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